

54th Days of Preventive Medicine International Congress

27-30. September 2022.
Niš, Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACT

Public Health Institute Niš

Faculty of Medicine,
University of Niš

Serbian Medical Society

Niš, 2022.

*122 years of Public Health Protection in Serbia
from regular preventive activities
to great challenges in COVID-19 pandemic time*

*122 године заштите јавног здравља у Србији
од редовних превентивних активности
до великих изазова у време пандемије COVID-19*

**PUBLIC HEALTH INSTITUTE NIŠ
FACULTY OF MEDICINE, UNIVERSITY OF NIŠ
SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY, NIŠ**

**54TH DAYS OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE
INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS**

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NIŠ, 2022.

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- **Environment and health**
- **Nutrition and health**
- **Microbiology today**
- **Current parasitosis**
- **Theoretical and practical problems of communicable diseases**
- **Theoretical and practical problems of non-communicable diseases**
- **Health promotion – challenges and solutions**
- **Preventive aspect of healthcare organization**
- **Application of information and communication tools in the health care system**

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7. PREDICTORS OF DISEASE SEVERITY IN PATIENTS WITH COVID-19

Đurić Milivoje¹, Makević Đurić M.², Kavečan I.³, Vujčić I.⁴, Maksimović J.⁴

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Objectives: To identify predictors of severe forms of COVID-19 defined as the need for assisted ventilation (non-invasive or invasive mechanical ventilation).

Methods: The research was conducted as a retrospective cohort study at the General hospital "Laza K. Lazarević" in Šabac for the period from 1.4.2020. to 14.11.2020. The relationship between demographic and clinical parameters of patients and the need for assisted ventilation was examined by logistic regression analysis.

Results: The study included 516 patients, 334 male subjects (64.7%), with the age of 60 and over (52.7%). The most commonly reported symptoms were fever (89%) and generalized weakness (68.8%). Mechanical ventilation was required by 44 patients, majority of whom were male (64.7%). The dominant comorbidities in mechanically ventilated group were hypertension (63.6%) and diabetes (22.7%). According to multivariate analysis independent risk factors for assisted ventilation were: obesity ($p=0.022$), duration of illness from onset to hospital admission more than seven days ($p=0.023$), oxygen saturation ($sO_2 < 90\%$) ($p=0.002$), arrhythmias ($p=0.001$), leukocytosis ($p=0.034$), lymphopenia $< 1.0 \times 10^9$ ($p=0.022$) and CRP > 50 mg/l ($p=0.002$).

Conclusion: The risk of assisted ventilation was higher in obese patients, with $sO_2 < 90\%$ on admission to hospital, duration of illness from onset to hospital admission more than seven days, arrhythmias, leukocytosis, lymphopenia $< 1.0 \times 10^9$ and CRP > 50 mg/l.

Keywords: COVID-19, comorbidities, risk factors, severity, assisted ventilation